

ABO Blood Group Polymorphism in Human: A Case Study

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Abstract

A study on ABO blood group polymorphism was done on human which show a variation in human population. the O blood group is the most common blood group having 33% and AB blood group is the least common blood group with 5.55% of people. Also, the negative blood group is very rare with comprising only 1% of the total people and it was A-ve. The incompatibility of Rh factor may lead to HDN resulting in severe anemia or death of child before or after birth.

Keywords: ABO blood group, polymorphism, genotype, HDN

Introduction

Polymorphism is a natural occurrence which is related to biodiversity, genetic variation and adaptation [1]. The ABO blood group system is the most common blood group system in human being and the blood groups are named after somenatural antigens present on the RBC's surfaces. It was the first reported and studied genetic polymorphism in human being. It is an example of multiple allele inheritance concerning three alleles – I^A , I^B and I^O located on the chromosome no. 9. So the A blood group has two possible combinations of genes or genotypes of $I^A I^O$ or $I^A I^A$; the B blood group has two possible combinations of $I^B I^O$ or $I^B I^B$; AB has only one combination of $I^A I^B$, whereas O has also one combination of $I^O I^O$, which indicate that A and B blood groups are co-dominant and O is recessive to both of A and B. Blood transfusions were first attempted around 1600 by transfusing animal blood into humans which proved disastrous. In 1900, Karl Landsteiner at the University of Vienna discovered why some blood transfusions were successful while others could be deadly. He discovered the ABO blood group system by mixing the red cells and serum of each of his staff and demonstrated that the serum of some people agglutinated the red cells of other [2]. From these early experiments, Landsteiner identified three types, called A, B and C (C was later to be re-named O for the German "Ohne", meaning "without", or "Zero", "null" in English). The fourth less frequent blood group AB, was discovered a year later. Landsteiner received the Nobel Prize in 1930 in physiology and medicine for his work. Majority of human also have an antigen termed as Rh factor (after the name of Rhesus monkey where it was first isolated & identified). Person having the antigen are called Rh^+ ve and those who have not are called Rh^- ve. Actually, there is no natural antibody against the Rh antigen, but can be induced by inoculating the antigen. Incompatibilities of blood groups transfusion leads to the agglutination of RBC, which also crack and its contents leak out in the body. The red blood cells contain hemoglobin which becomes toxic when outside the cell. This can have fatal consequences for the patient. The incompatibility of Rh factor may lead to HDN (Hemolytic Disease of Newborn), resulting in severe anemia or death of child before or after birth.

Materials and Methods

The primary data (blood samples) were collected from the students of Joya Gogoi College and other schools along with secondary data from different people from Dergaon, Golaghat, Assam from 2021-2023.

Materials required were-

1. Monoclonal Antibodies (Anti-A, Anti-B and Anti-D)
2. Ice tray
3. Blood Lancet
4. Alcohol swabs
5. Tooth picks

6. Sterile cotton balls
7. Clean glass slides

The Procedure followed is as follows-

1. Keep the monoclonal antibodies on an Ice tray.
2. On the three depressions of a glass slide mark with glass marker as A, B and D respectively.
3. Open an alcohol swab, and rub it at the area from where blood will be sampled (finger tip)
4. Open the Lancet cover; put pressure at the tip of the finger from where blood will be sampled. Prick the finger tip with the opened Lancet and discard the Lancet.
5. As blood starts oozing out, make a drop fall on the three depressions of glass slide marked as A, B and D respectively.
6. Place a cotton ball at the site where it was picked. Using the thumb, put pressure on the area to stop blood flow.
7. Take the Anti-A (Blue) bottle, resuspend the content and use the dropper to place a drop of the Mab in the first spot of the slide marked as A.
8. Take the Anti-B (Yellow) bottle, resuspend the content and use the dropper to place a drop of the Mab in the second spot of the slide marked as B.
9. Take the Anti-D (Colorless) bottle, resuspend the content and use the dropper to place a drop of the Mab in the third spot of the slide marked as D.
10. Use three separate tooth pick to mix the content in each of the separate three drops.
11. After mixing wait for few minutes to observe the result.

Conclusion drawn are-

1. If blood clumps in the spot marked as A = blood group will be "A"
2. If blood clumps in the spot marked as B = blood group will be "B"
3. If blood clump both in the spots marked as A and B= blood group will be "AB"
4. If no blood clump both in the spots marked as A and B = blood group will be "O"
5. If blood clumps in the spot marked as D = Rh will be "+ve"
6. If no blood clumps in the spot marked as D = Rh will be "-ve"

Results and Discussion

A total of 495 students and other people had been sampled and the frequency of different blood groups were O>A>B>AB=180>170>115>30. Thus, the O blood group is the most common blood group having 33% and AB blood group is the least common blood group with 5.55% of people. Also, the negative blood group is very rare with comprising only 1% of the total people and it was A^{-ve}. According to Ford (1940)[3], "Genetic polymorphism is the simultaneous occurrence in the same locality of two or more discontinuous forms in such proportions that the rarest of them cannot be maintained just by recurrent mutation or immigration". It is the natural selection which eliminates the bad allele from a population, but the different blood groups polymorphisms are seemingly never eliminated by natural selection and the reason came from the study of disease statistics by various researchers. As for example, there are various degree in susceptibility of disease cholera caused by the *Vibrio cholerae* by the four different blood groups are: O is most susceptible, AB is most resistant, A is more resistant than B [4]. Although O group have a greater life expectancy than other three types of blood groups, but highly prone to *Helicobacter pylori* causing the disease peptic ulcers [5,6]. According to Bjorkholmet *al.*[7], it has established colonies in the stomachs of approximately one –half the world's population.

Table 1: No. of people with different blood groups

Sl. No.	Blood groups	No. of people
1.	A	170(31.48%)
2.	B	115 (21.29%)
3.	AB	30(5.55%)
4.	O	180(33.33%)

5.	Rh Positive	490 (99%)
6.	Rh Negative	5 (1%)

Conclusion

Thus, genetic frequencies within different populations may vary;but they remain constant from generation to generation within population due to the fact that none of the alleles for these blood groups have a selective advantage over the other which resultsa balanced selection.A combination of selection against infectious diseases (e.g. plague and smallpox) and genetic drift and founder effects in small populations may ultimately explain the allele frequencies observed today.

References

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